

Mechanistic Insights into Chloride-Dependent Uncaging Reaction of Propargyl and Allene-Protected Substrates by Pd-Complexes

Thuany M. Ferreira,^[a] Claudio D. Navo,^[b] Jonathan P. Agnes,^[a] Filipe Cardozo,^[a] Daniela C. de Oliveira,^[c] Alfeu Zanotto Filho,^[d] Gonzalo Jiménez-Osés,^{*[b,e]} Josiel B. Domingos^{*[a]}

[a] T. M. Ferreira, J. P. Agnes, F. Cardozo, B. L. Albuquerque, J. B. Domingos

Laboratory of Biomimetic Catalysis (LaCBio)

Department of Chemistry - Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC)

Campus Trindade, 88040-900, Florianópolis - SC, Brazil.

E-mail: josiel.domingos@ufsc.br

[b] C. D. Navo, G. Jiménez-Osés

Center for Cooperative Research in Biosciences (CIC BioGUNE)

Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA)

Bizkaia Technology Park, Building 800, 48160 Derio (Spain).

Email: gonzalo.jimenez-oses@cicbiogune.es

[c] D. C. de Oliveira

Brazilian Synchrotron Light Laboratory (LNLS)

C. P. 6192, 13083-970, Campinas - SP, Brazil

[d] A. Zanotto Filho

Laboratory of Cancer Pharmacology (LabCancer)

Department of Pharmacology - Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC)

Campus Trindade, 88040-900, Florianópolis - SC, Brazil.

[e] G. Jiménez-Osés

Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science

48013 Bilbao, Spain.

Abstract: This study investigates the effect of chloride levels on the mode of action of palladium complexes for the activation of propargyl- and allene-protected fluorophores and chemotherapeutic drugs through uncaging reactions. Four Pd(II) complexes were synthesized and characterized using various spectroscopic techniques to confirm their structure and electronic properties. Kinetic studies and density functional theory calculations revealed that chloride ions in PBS significantly enhance catalytic efficiency, particularly for allenyl-protected substrates compared to propargylic counterparts. This enhancement is attributed to the neutral charge nature of the Pd complex. The data suggest that neutral complexes are less prone to chloride exchange by water molecules. Additionally, chloride ligands counterbalance the unusually high stability of the key σ -bound η^1 -Pd intermediates in the aquo complexes in PB, leading to an overall higher reactivity. These results highlight the impact of fine-tuning the electronic properties of the metal center through both designed ligands and environmental factors. Bench evaluations and tests with living breast cancer cells demonstrated that a Pd catalyst complex with a bidentate ligand effectively activates the prodrugs propargyl-5-fluorouracil (Prop-5FU) and allene-5-Fluorouracil (Alle-5FU), the latter being a novel prodrug. The Pd catalyst successfully released the active drug, inducing significant cell death, especially with Alle-5FU, which operates at lower catalyst concentrations than Pro-5FU.

Introduction

The advancement of bioorthogonal chemistry has revolutionized targeted cancer therapies by enabling the activation of prodrugs within the tumor microenvironment, thereby enhancing treatment efficacy and reducing systemic toxicity.^[1-5] Transition metal (TM) salts, complexes, and nanoparticles have been strategically utilized to trigger antineoplastic prodrugs, marking a significant leap toward precision medicine.^[6-16] Among these, palladium complexes are particularly noteworthy for their catalytic efficiency and the modifiability of their ligand environments.^[17] Bioorthogonal reactions catalyzed by Pd complexes facilitate the release of active drugs directly at the tumor site, maximizing therapeutic efficacy while minimizing systemic side effects.

Despite the promising potential of Pd complexes, their translation from the bench to clinical applications faces challenges, primarily related to the design of ligands that enhance solubility, stability, and biological targeting. Recent advances in ligand design have shown potential in increasing the in vivo stability and catalytic activity of Pd complexes, paving the way for more effective and targeted therapeutic strategies.^[18-20] Understanding the dynamic interplay between ligand design and tumor microenvironments is crucial for optimizing the modes of action and intrinsic physicochemical properties of these catalyst systems.

An often-overlooked aspect within these complex biological environments is the role of the surrounding aqueous medium on TM catalysts, particularly the impact of chloride ions prevalent in

physiological solutions such as phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). The coordinating abilities of chloride ions, coupled with their concentration gradients - which range from approximately 4-30 mmol L⁻¹ within cells to about 100-140 mmol L⁻¹ in extracellular fluids - are critical factors influencing the structure and activity of the catalysts. This is especially relevant for Pd(II) complexes, which frequently feature one or two labile sites engaged by chloride ions, crucial for ligand exchange and prodrug activation.

Previous studies by our research group have highlighted the impact of chloride ion concentrations on the kinetics of a negatively charged Pd(II)-catalyst in uncaging reactions. For instance, our research demonstrated that lower chloride concentrations, which mimic intracellular conditions, may enhance the reaction rates of Pd(II)-catalyzed uncaging reactions compared to higher chloride concentrations typical of extracellular environments. However, this enhancement is highly dependent on the caging group, as well the nature of the Pd catalyst.^[21]

Our current study aims to build on these findings by investigating the effects of chloride ion concentrations on the catalytic performance of Pd(II) complexes. We hypothesize that manipulating the ligands coordinated to the metal and the charge of the complex can result in variations in catalytic performance influenced by chloride ion concentrations. To rigorously test this hypothesis, we conducted a comprehensive mechanistic study employing a Pd-catalyzed reaction with *O*-propargyl and *O*-allenyl protected 4-methylumbelliferone model substrates. Our objective was to elucidate the effects of chloride ion concentrations within biological conditions on the kinetics of these uncaging reactions.

Furthermore, we extended our investigations to assess the efficiency of Pd complexes in facilitating the uncaging of a novel allenyl prodrug derivative of the chemotherapeutic agent 5-fluorouracil within a breast cancer cell line. This research not only enhances our understanding of the influence of chloride ions but also offers valuable insights into the potential application of Pd complexes for precise drug activation in cancer therapy.

Results and Discussion

Four palladium complexes were designed with different ligands surrounding the labile chloride atom coordinated to the Pd(II) atom, varying in complex charge. Bi- and tridentate ligands containing nitrogen and/or sulfur atoms were prepared, with ligand volume increased by attaching varying numbers of phenyl groups (Scheme 1). The selection of ligands was based on our hypothesis that sterically hindered *S,N*-type chelators would enhance catalytic efficiency by preventing inhibition during the catalytic cycle, while also providing stability in biological environments due to their compatibility with Pd(II) under Pearson's HSAB theory. The synthesis procedures for both ligands and complexes closely followed those outlined in the literature and are further detailed in the Supporting Information.

The complexes were first characterized by Synchrotron-based X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS). Analysis of the complexes in the XANES region indicates that the palladium oxidation state is 2+ in all complexes. This determination was made by measuring the position of the edge and comparing it to

the standards of Pd(0) edge at 24.350 keV and Pd(II) edges from K₂PdCl₄ at 24.354 keV and Pd(OAc)₂ at 24.352 keV (Figure 1A). The Pd XANES spectra of the metal foil exhibit a pronounced white line at 24.366 keV due to the unfilled d-band of palladium.

Scheme 1. Pd(II) complexes catalysts structures.

Comparing C1 to C3, where the initial coordination atoms around Pd are two sulfur and two chlorine atoms, the organic ligand attached to the sulfur atom differs. The most significant difference in the XANES spectra is observed in the white line region for C1, where it presents two distinct peaks, while C3 is smoother with one broad white line peak, despite the oxidation state of Pd remaining the same (Figure S1). These differences can be attributed to their distinct geometries caused by different ligands on their outer coordination shells.^[22] Similarly, comparing C2 to C4, where the closest coordination atoms are the same (first shell around Pd), the oxidation state is maintained. The differences between these complexes are due to the organic structures linked to the sulfur atoms, which is reflected in the lower amplitude of the XANES spectrum for C2.

This structural change is not observed in the C2 versus C4 comparison, even though they have different ligands, probably because the nitrogen atom is connected to both sulfur atoms in both samples, making the structure more rigid. Comparing C3 to C4, the difference in the first shell is the substitution of one chlorine atom in C3 with one nitrogen atom in C4. This results in a subtle difference in their XANES spectra, with C3 showing a slight shift to lower energy (~1 eV) compared to C4, similar to the effect of chloride presence in solution observed by Bazarkina and coworkers.^[23] However, since both C3 and C4 feature similar ligands (with three phenyl groups attached to each sulfur atom), the spectral differences are minimal. This suggests that the geometry is not significantly affected, likely due to the steric hindrance imposed by the bulky ligands, which could cause a distortion in the overall geometry. This observation is further supported by comparing C1 to C2; in this case, the substitution of one chlorine by one nitrogen in their first shells results in more obvious spectral differences, suggesting that a structural change is caused by the different ligands. The changes in interatomic distances, geometry, and electronic effects are responsible for the differences seen in the XANES spectra of these samples. The Pd complexes were further characterized by ¹H and ¹³C NMR, ESI-MS, and CHN as detailed in the Supporting Information.

Figure 1. (A) Normalized Pd K-edge XANES spectra of Pd complexes (C1 to C4); (B) Kinetic profiles for the uncaging reactions of Alle-4-MU and Prop-4-MU promoted by C1 complex; (C) Prop-4-MU and (D) Alle-4-MU, for the reactions promoted by the complexes (C2 to C4). Reactions conditions: [substrate] = 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, [C1] = 10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, [C2-C4] = 20 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, PBS buffer (5% DMSO), pH 7.4, 37°C.

Kinetic Analysis and Reactivity

To explore the activity of the complexes in uncaging reactions under biological conditions and verify the effect of buffer chloride ion levels, we conducted an in-depth kinetic analysis of the C-O cleavage reactions of propargyl (Prop-4-MU) and 1,2-allenyl protected 4-methylumbelliferone (Alle-4-MU) as model substrates (Figures 1B-D). Propargyl is one of the most employed caging groups for O/N functional groups of biomolecules, dyes, and drugs in uncaging reactions catalyzed by transition metals. Recently, the allenyl group has garnered attention due to its superior reactivity compared to the propargyl counterpart.^[21,24]

These investigations took place in aqueous phosphate-buffered (PB) or phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solutions, maintaining a constant pH of 7.4 and a temperature of 37 °C. The key distinction between these buffers is the presence of 140 mmol L⁻¹ of chloride ions in PBS, which allowed us to evaluate the specific influence of chloride levels in these reactions. Throughout the experiments, we meticulously monitored the appearance of

the phenolate product (4-methylumbelliferone, 4-MU) using UV-vis or fluorescence spectroscopy.

Our preliminary kinetic evaluations were conducted using both substrates to screen the performance of the Pd complexes, with PBS as the reaction medium. As shown in the kinetic profiles in Figure 1, the catalysts with the bidentate ligand and the least steric hindrance (C1) presented the best performance for both reactions. For the reaction involving the substrate Prop-4-MU, the half-life ($t_{1/2}$) is approximately 270 minutes, which is significantly longer than the half-life for the deallenylation reaction of Alle-4-MU ($t_{1/2}$ = 12 minutes), emphasizing the intrinsic superior reactivity of the allenyl caging group (Figure 1B). The lower performance of complexes C3 and C4 can be attributed to the -C(Ph)₃ group attached to the sulfur atom, which significantly decreased the solubility of the complexes and likely reduced the palladium's accessibility for substrate binding. Complex C2, possessing just one labile chloride ligand, also performed less effectively compared to the C1 catalyst (Figures 1C and 1D).

Table 1. Second-order rate constant (k_2)^a and product conversion in different reaction medium.

Entry	Catalyst	Substrate	Medium	k_2 (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	[Product] ^b (%)	Catalyst Reaction-Order	Substrate Reaction-Order
1	C1	Prop-4-MU	PB	16.0	33	1.1	0.5
2	C1	Prop-4-MU	PBS	6.9	46	0.9	2.1
3	C1	Alle-4-MU	PB	11.9	20	0.9	0.5
4	C1	Alle-4-MU	PBS	22.7	86	0.7	2.1

^a Aqueous phosphate-buffered media (ionic strength (I) = 140 mmol L⁻¹ (NaClO₄)). ^b Maximum product conversion with 50 mol% of Pd.

To gain a deeper understanding of C1's catalytic power, we performed a series of kinetic experiments comparing its activity in both reaction models. These included the determination of second-order rate constants, substrate and catalyst reaction orders, identification of the catalytic Pd species by poisoning experiments, and addition of a protein (BSA) to measure its catalytic performance in a more complex environment.

The data presented in Table 1 offers a detailed view of the second-order rate constants (k_2) and product conversions for palladium-catalyzed uncaging reactions using different substrates (Prop-4-MU and Alle-4-MU) and reaction media (PB and PBS). By examining these values, we can infer the catalytic efficiency and product yield, offering insight into the underlying mechanisms.

The data reveal that the Alle-4-MU substrate generally exhibits higher reactivity and product conversion compared to Prop-4-MU. For the C1 catalyst in PBS, the k_2 value for Alle-4-MU is 22.7 L mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ with 86% product conversion, compared to 6.9 L mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ and 46% conversion for Prop-4-MU (with 50 mol% of C1 in PBS, Table 1). Moreover, this k_2 surpasses a crucial criterion for a bioorthogonal reaction, which ideally should exhibit second-order rate constants greater than 10 L mol⁻¹ s⁻¹.^[25]

To analyze the effect of the chloride ions on the catalytic efficiency of C1, we monitored the reactions with Prop-4-MU and Alle-4-MU in PB and PBS buffers using increasing amounts of C1 (Figures S3 and S4, respectively). As we have shown in our previous work, the presence of chloride ions in PBS medium plays a crucial role in modulating the catalytic performance of the palladium catalysts.^[21] However, in contrast to our previous work where for the Allyl₂Pd₂Cl₂ catalyst, where chloride ions in PBS negatively impacted the catalytic efficiency, high concentration of Cl⁻ improves product conversion using the C1 catalyst with Alle-4-MU as a substrate. This highlights the complex nature of palladium catalysis in the presence of different amounts of chloride ions and underscores the importance of understanding the dynamic interactions between catalysts, substrates, and the reaction media. Of note, complete conversion is never observed with either Alle-4-MU or Prop-4-MU as substrates even when using high amounts of catalyst, suggesting the occurrence of some catalyst deactivation/inhibition process. This is especially affected in the case of Prop-4-MU, where the maximum conversion observed is 46%.

The reaction time-courses were numerically fitted using differential equations to two different kinetic models, both incorporating a catalyst deactivation/inhibition term in order to account for the observed plateauing at non-complete conversions; such models differ only in the orders of the substrate and products (0.5 or 1) in the productive and deactivation pathways, respectively, while the order of the catalyst was set to 1 in all cases. Excellent fits of the experimental data were obtained in all cases, regardless of the catalyst concentration and the kinetic model used (i.e., when the order of the substrate/products is set to a different value, each corresponding kinetic rate constant just adjusts accordingly).

The observed reaction orders for the C1 catalyst with both Prop-4-MU and Alle-4-MU substrates indicate a complex interplay between the catalyst, substrate, and the reaction medium, as the orders experimentally determined were 0.5 and 1 for the substrate and catalyst, respectively, in PB, while 2 and 1 for the substrate and catalyst, respectively, in PBS (Table 1). Assuming that the reaction follows a mechanism similar to previous works^[21] (i.e. the substrate coordinates to the metal, the complex reacts with water, and the payload is released) the variation of the reaction orders as a function of the medium suggests the appearance of one or more complexes prior to the formation of the active catalytic species affected notably by the presence or absence of chloride ions in the medium. As shown later, plausible reaction mechanisms for the observed results were interrogated through quantum mechanical calculations.

To gather further insights about the active Pd catalytic species, kinetic experiments were performed with the addition of CS₂ (6.0 equiv relative to the catalyst) and EDTA (10 equiv relative to the catalyst) to the reaction medium. These compounds selectively bind to Pd(0) and Pd(II), respectively, poisoning the catalyst and inhibiting its activity. Figures 2A and 2B show that the addition of EDTA during the course of the reactions with Prop-4-MU and Alle-4-MU, strongly inhibits the reactions. This indicates that Pd(II) is the active species in both cases. This is further supported by the results with the addition of CS₂ to the reactions, where the kinetic profiles remained unaltered, suggesting that it is unlikely that Pd(0) is the active species.

Figure 2. Additives effect for the uncaging reaction of (A) Prop-4-MU and (B) Alle-4-MU promoted by C1 complex. Reactions conditions: [Substrates] = 0.1 mmol L⁻¹, [Pd] = 50 μmol L⁻¹, PBS, pH: 7.4, 5% DMSO. Effect of BSA for the uncaging reaction of (C) Prop-4-MU and (D) Alle-4-MU promoted by C1 complex. Reactions conditions: [Substrates] = 100 μmol L⁻¹, [Pd] = 50 μmol L⁻¹, PBS, pH: 7.4, 5% DMSO.

The C1 catalyst was also tested in a more complex environment with the addition of the protein bovine serum albumin (BSA). Due to its hydrophobic pockets, BSA can interact with the catalyst, allowing the ligand to interact, while the *trans* positions (chloride ions) are exposed to interact with the substrate. BSA has a high similarity to human serum albumin (HSA). When 3.0 mequiv, 10.5 mequiv, and 101.5 mequiv were added to the reaction with Prop-4-MU in PBS (Figure 2C), the kinetic profiles showed distinct alterations, with a decrease in the reaction rate and product conversion at higher BSA concentrations. At even higher BSA concentrations (0.50 equiv and 1.0 equiv), the conversion after 400 minutes was less than 2%. This observation presents a challenge because HSA is the most abundant protein in the human body.

Conversely, when the substrate Alle-4-MU was tested (Figure 2D), the reaction kinetic profile did not change with the addition of 3.0 and 10.5 mequiv, indicating that this substrate is less affected by BSA addition. However, when 101.5 mequiv was added, the reaction rate and product conversion decreased. These results indicate that the substrate caging group also influences the activity of the Pd catalyst in more complex media.

Quantum Mechanical Calculations and Proposed Mechanisms

First, we analyzed the sequential substitution of both chlorine atoms in C1 (Pd(BPTE)Cl₂) by water molecules (Table 2, Figure S11). We observed that both substitution steps are quite endergonic, especially the second one ($\Delta G \sim 15$ and 34 kcal mol⁻¹ for the first and second substitution step, respectively) with activation energies of $\Delta G^\ddagger \sim 17$ and 32 kcal mol⁻¹ for the first and second substitution step, respectively. These data suggest that, in media with high chloride concentrations (PBS), the predominant catalyst species is the dichloride form, whereas in lower concentration environments, the chloro-aquo species might play some role. A similar trend was obtained for the previously reported catalyst Pd(Allyl)Cl₂, with lower values, particularly for the second substitution step ($\Delta G^\ddagger \sim 18$ kcal mol⁻¹; $\Delta G \sim 17$ kcal mol⁻¹).^[21] This suggests that the negatively charged species [Pd(Allyl)Cl₂]⁻ is more prone to undergo chloride substitution to water molecules than the inherently neutral C1, particularly in media with low chloride concentrations (PB).

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Table 2. Calculated Free Gibbs energy (kcal mol⁻¹) for the consecutive reactions of catalysts C1 and Pd(Allyl)Cl₂ with one and two molecules of water to afford the corresponding mono- and diaquo species.

Species	Pd(BPTE)Cl ₂ (C1) (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Pd(Allyl)Cl ₂ (kcal mol ⁻¹)
PdLCl ₂	0.0	0.0
PdLCl ₂ +H ₂ O_TS	17.1	11.3
PdL(H ₂ O)Cl	14.6	6.2
PdL(H ₂ O)Cl+H ₂ O_TS	32.2	18.1
PdL(H ₂ O) ₂	33.9	16.9

We then analyzed the deallylation reaction envisioning a similar mechanism than the previously reported one for the Pd(Allyl)Cl₂/Pd(Allyl)(H₂O) catalyst^[21] (i.e. coordination of the substrate to the metal center, hydration of the unsaturations, and final elimination) (Figure 3A). To model the reaction in media with high chloride concentrations (PBS) and considering the low tendency of the palladium complex C1 to interchange chloride ions to water molecules described above, we used the dichloro species C1 as the starting catalyst. The first step involves the coordination of the allene group of Alle-4-Mu (abbreviated as **A**) to Pd with simultaneous release of a chloride ligand. As with Pd-allyl complexes, π -bond coordination (**B**) is thermodynamically more favored than the catalytically active σ -bond coordination of Pd to the allene's central carbon atom in a η^1 fashion (**C**) ($\Delta\Delta G_{\sigma-\pi} \sim 7$ kcal mol⁻¹). The attack of a water molecule to the inner carbon of the allene in **C** (**TS1**, $\Delta G^\ddagger \sim 27$ kcal mol⁻¹) is the rate-determining step (RDS), and evolves to intermediate **D**. Notably, no stationary points were located at the chosen level of theory for the subsequent intramolecular proton transfer to intermediate **E** or the following decaying of phenol (**TS2**); in fact, relaxed scans along the breaking C–O bond from low-energy conformations always show downhill profiles (Figure S11), resulting in the direct formation of σ -bound complex **F**. At a lower theoretical level, however, such high-energy stationary points could indeed be located, revealing a considerably flat potential energy surface (PES) for this stage of the global reaction (Figure S18).

At this point, the process is slightly endergonic ($\Delta G \sim 5$ kcal mol⁻¹), and three possible scenarios may happen: 1) substitution of the allenol molecule by a chloride ion to regenerate the initial

catalyst; 2) substitution of the allenol molecule by another Alle-4-MU molecule to regenerate the active Pd species; and 3) further hydration of the allenol within the complex (Figure 3A). The first two scenarios are interlaced and lead to catalytic turnover; however, both require either direct breaking of a strong Pd–C σ -bond, or transformation to a more labile and less stable π -bond (**G**) ($\Delta\Delta G_{\pi-\sigma} \sim 2$ kcal mol⁻¹). Of note, the first scenario involves a slightly exergonic and potentially reversible ($\Delta G \sim -3$ kcal mol⁻¹, i.e. in equilibrium) global reaction.

On the contrary, hydration of the complexed allenol has a low intrinsic activation barrier (**TS3**, $\Delta G_i^\ddagger \sim 15$ kcal mol⁻¹ from **F**) and leads to a quite inert σ -coordinated hydroxypropanal after tautomerization and deprotonation of the resulting intermediate, as previously reported for PdCl₄²⁻ catalyst.^[26] This scenario limits catalyst turnover and is hypothesized to cause the strong catalyst inhibition/deactivation observed experimentally.

On the other hand, when the same mechanism is computed from the chloro-aquo catalyst species, Pd(BPTE)(H₂O)Cl – considered to be the major species in media with low chloride concentrations (PB) – a very similar profile is obtained, although with higher energies ($\Delta\Delta G^\ddagger \sim 5$ kcal mol⁻¹ at the RDS), which translates into a slower reaction rate. In this case, we propose that substrate **A** would substitute the chloride atom, leading to π -allene(aquo) complex **B'**, assuming thermodynamics would favor this scenario since water concentration is exceedingly high in the buffer (>50 mol L⁻¹). Notably, π -complex **B'** and σ -complex **C'** are now virtually isoenergetic ($\Delta\Delta G_{\sigma-\pi} \sim 1$ kcal mol⁻¹), since Pd is even more electron-withdrawing in the absence of negatively charged ligands (the total charge in such Pd(BPTE)(H₂O)(allene) intermediates is +2), but still higher in energy than **B** and **C** ($\Delta\Delta G \sim 9$ and 3 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively). Additionally, species **F'** and **G'** are also higher in energy than **F** and **G** ($\Delta\Delta G \sim 6$ -7 kcal mol⁻¹), respectively, and the subsequent hydration step (**TS3'**) is slightly more favorable ($\Delta G_i^\ddagger \sim 14$ kcal mol⁻¹ from **F'**). Overall, these results suggest a much slower turnover and an even stronger catalyst inhibition with Pd(BPTE)(H₂O)Cl compared to Pd(BPTE)Cl₂.

Altogether, these results suggest that, in PBS the reaction would be faster and would lead to higher conversion ratios than in PB, in agreement with the experiments. However, the exact contribution of the many catalytic species that are possible in each media still has to be ascertained.

Finally, the reactions with Prop-4-MU (abbreviated as **A_{prop}**) were also calculated, yielding similar energy profiles and trends; some of the elusive stationary points discussed above for Alle-4-Mu could be located in this case. The same products were obtained, albeit at a higher energy cost, suggesting lower reaction rates and conversion ratios (Figure S17), as observed experimentally. This may be due to the inherent inability of the propargyl group to coordinate Pd through a σ -bond along the reaction, making it much less reactive than the allene derivative.

A: Mechanism for O-deallylation reaction catalyzed by Pd(BPTE)(X)Cl in water

Figure 3. Proposed mechanism and minimum energy pathway (MEP) calculated with **PCM(H₂O)/M06/6-311+G(d,p);SDD(Pd)** for the O-deallylation reaction of **Alle-4-MU** (abbreviated as **A**) using Pd(BPTE)Cl₂ (orange) and Pd(BPTE)(H₂O)Cl (green) as catalysts.

Activation of Prop- and Alle-5-Fluorouracil Prodrugs by the C1 Complex

The catalytic efficiency of the C1 catalyst in depropargylation and deallylation reactions was further assessed through the activation of the prodrugs allene-5-fluorouracil (Alle-5FU) and

propargyl-5-fluorouracil (Prop-5FU), Figure 1A. Alle-5FU is a novel prodrug developed based on the superior results observed in deallylation reactions. Prop-5FU was used for comparative purposes to evaluate the in vitro performance of the C1 catalyst across different substrate types. Initially, these reactions were evaluated in vitro in PBS medium, with the reaction products

RESEARCH ARTICLE

analyzed by HPLC. The chromatograms (Figure S19) indicate that the cleavage of the caging groups mediated by C1 results in 28% product conversion for the Alle-5FU prodrug after 48 hours. For the Prop-5FU prodrug, a 25% product conversion was observed after 48 hours. These findings demonstrate that the C1 catalyst is effective in activating these prodrugs, with the allenyl substrate showing a slightly higher product conversion than the propargylic substrate.

To determine prodrug conversion in a biological context, we performed experiments in the breast cancer cell line MDA-MB 231. The results for Prop-5FU (Figures 4B and Figure S20) indicate that a concentration of 200 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ was insufficient to induce cell death, whereas the same concentration of the active drug resulted in 75% cell death. This underscores the safety of the Prop-5FU prodrug. When the C1 catalyst, at a concentration of 200 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, was combined with the Prop-5FU prodrug, the cleavage reaction occurred, liberating the active drug within the cells, which subsequently resulted in 45% cell death across all substrate concentrations (200, 100, and 50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$). Lower concentrations of C1 did not induce cell death at any prodrug concentration (data not shown).

The Alle-5FU prodrug also demonstrated safety with its administration below the 200 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ concentration (Figure 4C and Figure S20). However, in contrast with the propargylic prodrug, when the same cells were treated with the Alle-5FU prodrug, a lower concentration of the catalyst was required to cleave the caging group. Using 50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of C1, no cell death was observed. However, when combined with Alle-5FU, 40% of cell density reduction was achieved, demonstrating that this prodrug is more readily activated in complex environments and requires less catalyst to achieve effective drug release inside the cell. The combination of the Alle-5FU prodrug and C1 catalyst was also effective in inducing cell death in a B16F10 murine melanoma cell line (Figure 4D), indicating the versatility of this catalytic drug delivery system across different cell lines.

These results highlight the potential of the C1 catalyst for selective and efficient activation of prodrugs in both simple and complex biological environments, with a particular advantage observed for the Alle-5FU prodrug in reducing the required catalyst concentration for effective therapeutic action.

Figure 4. (A) Uncaging reaction of prodrugs prop-5-FU and alle-5FU. (B) Evaluation of tumor cells treated with the C1 catalyst and the prodrugs Prop-5FU and Alle-5FU with MDA-MB 231 breast cancer cells line, testing the combination of 200 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of the C1 catalyst with concentrations of 200 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, 100 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, and 50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of the prodrug Prop-5FU. (C) Subsequently, data from the combination of treatment of 50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of the catalyst with concentrations of 200 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, 100 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, and 50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of Alle-5FU in the MDA-MB 231 cell line are presented. In (D), the effect of 50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of the catalyst combined with 200 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of Alle-5FU in B16F10 tumor cell line was tested. * Different from control or vehicle control groups; \$ Different from groups treated only with the prodrug (at the same concentrations); # Different from the group treated only with the C1 catalyst (One-way ANOVA, post hoc Bonferroni; $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

This study synthesized and evaluated four palladium complexes for their catalytic efficiency in depropargylation and deallylation reactions, focusing on prodrug activation. The C1 catalyst, a neutral bidentate Pd complex, demonstrated superior performance, particularly with the novel prodrug allene-5-fluorouracil (Alle-5FU). Kinetic studies showed that chloride ions in PBS significantly enhance catalytic activity, with Alle-4-MU exhibiting higher reactivity than Prop-4-MU. DFT studies attribute this enhancement to the neutral charge nature of the C1 complex, which is less prone to chloride exchange by water molecules in a biological-type environment compared to negatively charged ones. Furthermore, chloride ligands in PBS mitigate the exceptionally high stability of the crucial σ -bound η^1 -Pd intermediates within the aquo complexes in PB, resulting in an overall increase in reactivity at high chloride concentrations. These findings underscore the significance of adjusting the electronic characteristics of the metal center through both engineered ligands and reaction media.

In vitro evaluations confirmed the C1 catalyst's efficacy and safety in biological environments, with the Alle-5FU prodrug requiring lower catalyst concentrations to achieve significant cell death. These findings highlight the C1 catalyst's potential for selective and efficient prodrug activation, offering a promising approach for targeted cancer therapy. Understanding the interplay between catalysts, substrates, and reaction conditions is crucial for optimizing palladium-catalyzed reactions in bioorthogonal chemistry and targeted therapeutics.

Supporting Information

The authors have cited additional references within the Supporting Information.^[27–33]

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the Brazilian National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) for the fellowships awarded to JPA, FC and JBD as well as financial support (process 408534/2022-2), and Foundation for Research and Innovation of the State of Santa Catarina (FAPESC) for the fellowship awarded to TMF. We also extend our gratitude to MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 for grants PID2021-125946OB-I00 and PDC2022-133725-C22 to GJO and CEX2021-001136-S to CIC bioGUNE. Additionally, the authors are thankful to CAPES Print Call - Program for Institutional Internationalization for supporting JBD (process 88887.310560/2018-00). This research used facilities of the Brazilian Synchrotron Light Laboratory (LNLS). The EMA and XDS beamline staff is acknowledged for the assistance during the experiments under the proposals 20221845. The authors also thank to LABIME and CentralCROM at UFSC for ESI-MS and LC-MS analysis.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords: Palladium Complexes • Bioorthogonal Uncaging Reactions • Reaction Kinetics • 5-Fluorouracil Prodrug • Breast Cancer

References

- [1] L. Taiariol, C. Chaix, C. Farre, E. Moreau, *Chem. Rev.* **2022**, *122*, 340–384.
- [2] W. Yi, P. Xiao, X. Liu, Z. Zhao, X. Sun, J. Wang, L. Zhou, G. Wang, H. Cao, D. Wang, Y. Li, *Signal Transduct. Target. Ther.* **2022**, *7*, 1–25.
- [3] E. Kozma, M. Bojtár, P. Kele, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62*, e202303198.
- [4] H. Zhang, J. Wang, R. Han, B. Sun, C. Luo, *TRENDS Chem.* **2023**, *5*, 697–710.
- [5] Q. Fu, S. Shen, P. Sun, Z. Gu, Y. Bai, X. Wang, Z. Liu, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2023**, *52*, 7737–7772.
- [6] H. Y. Shu, R. D. Zhu, J. Wu, X. H. Liu, J. B. Shi, *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.* **2021**, *21*, 2205–2212.
- [7] *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2021**, *61*, 32–42.
- [8] P. Destito, C. Vidal, F. Lopez, J. L. Mascarenas, *Chem.-Eur. J.* **2021**, DOI 10.1002/chem.202003927.
- [9] E. Latocheski, G. M. D. Forno, T. M. Ferreira, B. L. Oliveira, G. J. L. Bernardes, J. B. Domingos, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2020**, *49*, 7710–7729.
- [10] Y. Liu, Y. Bai, *ACS Appl. Bio Mater.* **2020**, *3*, 4717–4746.
- [11] M. Martínez-Calvo, J. L. Mascareñas, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *359*, 57–79.
- [12] *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **2018**, *53*, 106–114.
- [13] M. O. N. van de L'Isle, M. C. Ortega-Liebana, A. Unciti-Broceta, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2021**, *61*, 32–42.
- [14] A. Sousa-Castillo, A. Mariño-López, B. Puértolas, M. A. Correa-Duarte, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62*, e202215427.
- [15] X. Wan, Y. Zhang, Y. Nie, K. Zhang, Z. Jin, Z. Zhang, L. Gan, X. Liu, J. He, *Transl. CANCER Res.* **2023**, *12*, 2181–2196.
- [16] Q. Fu, C. Wei, M. Wang, *ACS Nano* **2024**, *18*, 12049–12095.
- [17] H. Zhang, X. Qin, J. Wang, L. Ma, T. Chen, *Sci. China Chem.* **2023**, DOI 10.1007/s11426-023-1615-1.
- [18] *Catal. Today* **2023**, *418*, 114116.
- [19] H.-T. Hsu, B. M. Trantow, R. M. Waymouth, P. A. Wender, *Bioconjug. Chem.* **2016**, *27*, 376–382.
- [20] *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2014**, *21*, 128–135.
- [21] G. M. Dal Forno, E. Latocheski, C. D. Navo, B. L. Albuquerque, A. L. St John, F. Avenier, G. Jiménez-Osés, J. B. Domingos, *Chem. Sci.* **2024**, DOI 10.1039/D3SC06408E.
- [22] Y. Mei, B. Etschmann, W. Liu, D. Sherman, S. Barnes, M. Fiorentini, T. Seward, D. Testemale, J. Brugger, *Geochim. Cosmochim. ACTA* **2015**, *161*, 128–145.
- [23] E. F. Bazarkina, G. S. Pokrovski, J.-L. Hazemann, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* **2014**, *146*, 107–131.
- [24] J. Wang, S. Zheng, Y. Liu, Z. Zhang, Z. Lin, J. Li, G. Zhang, X. Wang, J. Li, P. R. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 15118–15121.
- [25] E. M. Sletten, C. R. Bertozzi, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2011**, *44*, 666–676.
- [26] S. E. Coelho, F. S. S. Schneider, D. C. de Oliveira, G. L. Tripodi, M. N. Eberlin, G. F. Caramori, B. de Souza, J. B. Domingos, *ACS Catal.* **2019**, *9*, 3792–3799.
- [27] M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, X. Li, M. Caricato, A. V. Marenich, J. Bloino, B. G. Janesko, R. Gomperts, B. Mennucci, H. P. Hratchian, J. V. Ortiz, A. F. Izmaylov, J. L. Sonnenberg, Williams, F. Ding, F. Lipparini, F. Egidi, J. Goings, B. Peng, A. Petrone, T. Henderson, D. Ranasinghe, V. G. Zakrzewski, J. Gao, N. Rega, G. Zheng, W. Liang, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, T.

Vreven, K. Throssell, J. A. Montgomery Jr., J. E. Peralta, F. Ogliaro, M. J. Bearpark, J. J. Heyd, E. N. Brothers, K. N. Kudin, V. N. Staroverov, T. A. Keith, R. Kobayashi, J. Normand, K. Raghavachari, A. P. Rendell, J. C. Burant, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, M. Cossi, J. M. Millam, M. Klene, C. Adamo, R. Cammi, J. W. Ochterski, R. L. Martin, K. Morokuma, O. Farkas, J. B. Foresman, D. J. Fox, **2016**.

[28] Y. Zhao, D. G. Truhlar, *Theor. Chem. Acc.* **2008**, *120*, 215–241.

[29] P. J. Hay, W. R. Wadt, *J. Chem. Phys.* **1985**, *82*, 299–310.

[30] G. Scalmani, M. J. Frisch, *J. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *132*, 114110.

[31] R. F. Ribeiro, A. V. Marenich, C. J. Cramer, D. G. Truhlar, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2011**, *115*, 14556–14562.

[32] H. P. Hratchian, H. B. Schlegel, *J. Chem. Phys.* **2004**, *120*, 9918–9924.

[33] H. P. Hratchian, H. B. Schlegel, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2005**, *1*, 61–69.

Entry for the Table of Contents

Exploring the impact of chloride ions, this study highlights the high performance of a Pd(II) complex in the deallylation uncaging reaction of an allene-protected fluorophore and a chemotherapeutic drug. The Pd complex demonstrated superior performance in high chloride concentrations, while the novel Alle-5-Fluorouracil prodrug was effectively activated at low concentrations of the Pd complex, underscoring its potential for targeted drug activation in cancer therapy.